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New interface element with non-coincident nodes to simulate discrete damage in composite laminate

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1. Introduction & problematic
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5. Bending curvature consideration
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1. Introduction & problematic : context

- Increase of composite materials in aeronautical industry because of their high strength-to-weight ratio
- Vulnerability to out of plane stresses as low velocity impact
- Complex failure phenomena

[Fawcett, 2006]

[Aymerich, 2013]

[Enfedaque et al., 2010]

→ Over-sizing and high sizing costs

→ Numerical EF modelling

1. Introduction & problematic : Discrete Ply Model (DPM) [Bouvet et al., 2009]

[Hongkarnjanakul, 2013]

[Hongkarnjanakul, 2013]

Advantages

- Good representation of discrete damages
- Coupling of different failure modes
- Low number of material parameters

Drawbacks

- Coincident nodes between two consecutive plies
- Only standard ply orientation (0° , 90° , $\pm 45^\circ$)
- Distance between two matrix cracking imposed
- High computation times

1. Introduction & problematic : DPM limitations

DPM mesh imposes to link two characteristic length which are totally independent :

1. Element length \rightarrow Fiber failure

Longer than the element width

[Bazant, 1983]

2. Element width \rightarrow Distance between matrix cracking

Link with the intralaminar and interlaminar coupling

[Leopold and Harder, 2016]

[Maimi et al., 2015]

1. Introduction & problematic : DPM improvement

Objectives :

- Make the element length and width independent;
- Use longer element in the fiber direction by keeping the width to thickness ratio;
- Use cohesive element to simulate delamination with non coincident nodes;
- Use non usual stacking sequence;
- Decrease computational time.

How to manage cohesive zone with non coincident nodes ?

Kinematic sticking by adding nodes in the model → make the model heavy

1. Introduction & problematic : DPM improvement

New type of mesh with an user element :

→ Today only focus on 8-nodes interface element made with 4 sides overlapping zone

2. New interface element formulation :

$$\begin{bmatrix} U_{xP1} \\ \vdots \\ U_{xP8} \end{bmatrix} = \underline{\underline{\pi}} \begin{bmatrix} U_{x1} \\ \vdots \\ U_{x8} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\underline{\underline{\pi}} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 - \lambda_5 & \lambda_5 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \lambda_6 & 1 - \lambda_6 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 - \lambda_7 & \lambda_7 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \lambda_8 & 1 - \lambda_8 \\ 1 - \lambda_1 & 0 & 0 & \lambda_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 - \lambda_2 & \lambda_2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_3 & 1 - \lambda_3 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \lambda_4 & 0 & 0 & 1 - \lambda_4 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} F_{xP1} \\ \vdots \\ F_{xP8} \end{bmatrix} = \underline{\underline{K}} \begin{bmatrix} U_{xP1} \\ \vdots \\ U_{xP8} \end{bmatrix}$$

2. New interface element formulation :

$$\underline{\underline{K}} = \begin{pmatrix} k1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -k1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & k2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -k2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & k3 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -k3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & k4 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -k4 \\ -k1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & k1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -k2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & k2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -k3 & 0 & 0 & 0 & k3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -k4 & 0 & 0 & 0 & k4 \end{pmatrix}$$

[Hongkarnjanakul, 2013]

Degradation of the global stiffness matrix until
the good energy rate is dissipated

$$\begin{bmatrix} F_{xP1} \\ \vdots \\ F_{xP8} \end{bmatrix} = \underline{\underline{\pi}}^t \underline{\underline{K}} \underline{\underline{\pi}} \begin{bmatrix} U_{x1} \\ \vdots \\ U_{x8} \end{bmatrix}$$

3. DCB tests and results : material and specimen

UD T700/M21 :

E_1^t (GPa)	E_1^c (GPa)	E_t (GPa)	ν_{1t}	G_{1t} (GPa)	G_{1z} (GPa)
130	100	7.7	0.3	4.75	2.9
ϵ_t^0	ϵ_c^0	σ^{crush} (MPa)	G_t^f (N/mm)	G_c^f (N/mm)	
0.018	-0.0125	250	130	40	
σ_t^f (MPa)	τ_{1t}^f (GPa)	G_{1c}^d (N/mm)	G_{11c}^d (N/mm)		
60	110	0.5	1.8		

3. DCB tests and results : different mesh configuration tested

3. DCB tests and results : results

4. Bending curvature issue

5. Bending curvature consideration : global bending calculation

$$\begin{cases} z(0) = z_A \\ z(L) = z_B \\ z'(0) = \theta_A + \frac{z_B - z_A}{L} \\ z'(L) = \theta_B + \frac{z_B - z_A}{L} \end{cases}$$

$$z(x) = \alpha + \beta x + \gamma x^2 + \delta x^3$$

$$\begin{cases} \alpha = z_A \\ \beta = \theta_A + \frac{z_B - z_A}{L} \\ \gamma = \frac{-(2\theta_A + \theta_B)}{L} \\ \delta = \frac{\theta_A + \theta_B}{L^2} \end{cases}$$

$$z(x) = z_A + \theta_A x + \frac{z_B - z_A}{L} x - \frac{(2\theta_A + \theta_B)}{L} x^2 + \frac{\theta_A + \theta_B}{L^2} x^3$$

$$x = \lambda L$$

$$z(\lambda) = (1 - \lambda)z_A + \lambda z_B + \lambda \theta_A L - (2\theta_A + \theta_B)\lambda^2 L + (\theta_A + \theta_B)\lambda^3 L$$

$$z(\lambda) = (1 - \lambda)z_A + \lambda z_B$$

$$\Delta z(\lambda) = \lambda \theta_A L - (2\theta_A + \theta_B)\lambda^2 L + (\theta_A + \theta_B)\lambda^3 L$$

5. Bending curvature consideration : implementation

5. Bending curvature consideration : implementation

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \Delta z P1 = \lambda_1 \theta_1 L_{12} - (2\theta_1 + \theta_2) \lambda_1^2 L_{12} + (\theta_1 + \theta_2) \lambda_1^3 L_{12}^2 \\ \Delta z P2 = (1 - \lambda_2) \theta_2 L_{12} - (2\theta_2 + \theta_1) (1 - \lambda_2)^2 L_{12} + (\theta_2 + \theta_1) (1 - \lambda_2)^3 L_{12}^2 \\ \Delta z P3 = (1 - \lambda_3) \theta_3 L_{43} - (2\theta_3 + \theta_4) (1 - \lambda_3)^2 L_{43} + (\theta_3 + \theta_4) (1 - \lambda_3)^3 L_{43}^2 \\ \Delta z P4 = \lambda_4 \theta_4 L_{43} - (2\theta_4 + \theta_3) \lambda_4^2 L_{43} + (\theta_4 + \theta_3) \lambda_4^3 L_{43}^2 \\ \Delta z P5 = (1 - \lambda_5) \theta_5 L_{65} - (2\theta_5 + \theta_6) (1 - \lambda_5)^2 L_{65} + (\theta_5 + \theta_6) (1 - \lambda_5)^3 L_{65}^2 \\ \Delta z P6 = \lambda_6 \theta_6 L_{65} - (2\theta_6 + \theta_5) \lambda_6^2 L_{65} + (\theta_6 + \theta_5) \lambda_6^3 L_{65}^2 \\ \Delta z P7 = \lambda_7 \theta_7 L_{78} - (2\theta_7 + \theta_8) \lambda_7^2 L_{78} + (\theta_7 + \theta_8) \lambda_7^3 L_{78}^2 \\ \Delta z P8 = (1 - \lambda_8) \theta_8 L_{78} - (2\theta_8 + \theta_7) (1 - \lambda_8)^2 L_{78} + (\theta_8 + \theta_7) (1 - \lambda_8)^3 L_{78}^2 \end{array} \right.$$

6. DCB & ENF test and results : DCB

6. DCB & ENF test and results : ENF

6. DCB & ENF test and results : computational time

DCB

ENF

7. Conclusion & perspectives

- ✓ New interface element validate in mode I and mode II to simulate delamination between $0^\circ/90^\circ$ or $90^\circ/0^\circ$ interface
- ✓ Use of different ply thickness respecting the ration thickness/between two matrix cracking
- ✓ Decrease of computational time
- x The new interface element shall be extend for other orientation ply interface as $45^\circ/-45^\circ$ or $0^\circ/45^\circ$...
- x The new interface element shall be validate with an impact simulation